

"THE CRUCIAL ROLE OF POLYMER IN THE HEAT TRANSFER FROM ONE FIBER TO ANOTHER IN POLYMER / CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES."

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to propose evidence for the important role played by the polymer in a composite to enhance the thermal conductance of a fair contact between the fibers and hence the thermal conductivity of the composite. For this, the thermal conductivities of a series of chopped pitch-based carbon fibers felts and polycarbonate / pitch-based carbon fibers composites in which the arrays of fibers were about the same were measured in two perpendicular directions. It is shown that the thermal conductivity of the felt is higher in the composite compared with the thermal conductivity of the neat felt. Furthermore, a strong effect of the fiber orientation is observed.

Keywords : Thermal conductivity, thermal contact resistance, composite, polymer, carbon fiber

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent developments in thermal management have given rise to new applications involving composite materials. Because of their outstanding properties and of the wide range of fabrication processes, thermoplastic polymers filled with chopped highly thermally conductive pitch-based carbon fibers are good candidates for such applications.

Up to now, most of the research works were aimed at determining the influence of the filler (1, 2) and, to a smaller extent, the filler/matrix interface (3) on the thermal conductivity of composites. However, further investigations are still required to understand the exact mechanisms ruling heat transfer from the fiber to the matrix and conversely (4). Indeed, the thermal contact resistances between chopped fibers separated by polymer are responsible for the decrease of the thermal conductivity of these composites compared with the same type of material filled with continuous fibers (5).

We propose here to demonstrate the very important role played by the polymer to transfer the heat from one fiber to another inside the composite. For this, the thermal conductivities of a series of polymer/pitch-based carbon fiber composites have been measured as a function of the fiber volume fraction. In order to take into account the effect of orientation of the fibers, these measurements were performed along two perpendicular directions. Afterwards, a series of felts of identical carbon fibers with similar lengths and orientations have been realised and the same thermal conductivity measurements were performed.

2. TECHNIQUES OF MEASUREMENT

2.1. Out-of-plane thermal conductivity

The out-of-plane thermal conductivity (see figure 1) was measured at 35°C by means of a home-made "Heat Flux Meter". The principle of this technique is based on the steady state guarded comparative method : a given difference in temperature is applied on the faces of the sample and the resulting heat flux flowing through the sample is measured. This flux is then compared with the ones observed across references of known thermal conductivities, thus yielding the thermal conductivity of the sample.

The samples of felt were encapsulated in a disk-shaped container made in Vespel™ that was 32 mm in diameter and 3 mm thick. Good thermal contacts between the felt and the inner faces of the disk as well as between the container and the measurement device were assured by means of a silicone grease. A correction of the measured values was performed in order to take into account the contribution of the container to the measured thermal conductance which is the sum of those of the container and the felt.

Measurement of the disk-shaped composites materials were directly performed on the samples, without resort to the container. In this case, no correction of the measured values was required.

Figure 1 : Direction of the heat flux for the out-of-plane thermal conductivity measurement

2.2. In-plane thermal conductivity

The principle used for the in-plane thermal conductivity measurement was based on the four probe technique (see figure2). However, in order to minimise the strong influence of radiative heat losses, a heated guard surrounding the sample was added. A complete description of the experimental set-up is given elsewhere (5).

In this arrangement, the samples are 32 mm long, 5 mm wide and 3 mm thick.

In this paper, the thermal conductivity (K) is always given in [$\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$].

Figure 2 : Direction of the heat flux for the in-plane thermal conductivity measurement.

3. MATERIALS

The fibers used for these experiments were P55 pitch-based carbon fibers from AMOCO. Their good room temperature (6) thermal conductivity, $100 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, makes them a serious candidate for thermal management applications. In addition, when incorporated in a matrix, their rather low

electrical resistivity ($10^{-5}\Omega\text{m}$) allows them to address the field of all applications requiring moderate electrically conductive composite materials.

For the purpose of this experiment, the fibers were cut manually by means of series of razor blades strung on a rod and separated by 1 mm thick interleaves. This operation resulted in providing us with fibers that were about 1 mm long.

The polymer used to make the composite materials was Polycarbonate Lexan 145 from GE Plastics. Its room temperature thermal conductivity is $0.2 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ at room temperature. An amorphous polymer was chosen in order to avoid a matrix with different crystallinity degrees since the crystallinity degree may have a strong influence on the thermal conductivity of a polymer.

All the fiber concentrations referred to in this paper are always volume concentrations and are noted Vf.

3.1. Fabrication of the felts.

The felts were fabricated into two different shapes in order to obtain samples with the geometries required by the two measurement techniques. Both types of felts were build up by stacking and pressing successively several layers of chopped fibers. This resulted in a strong orientation of the chopped fibers that were roughly evenly dispersed in planes perpendicular to the pressing direction.

For the in-plane measurements, the felt in the form of a slab was surrounded by a cigarette paper in order to make it rigid enough to support itself. Furthermore, both extremities were dipped into paraffin wax to allow better heat distribution at the ends of the samples and to improve contacts between the samples and the sample holder.

For the out-of-plane measurements, the felts were build up in the capsule described above (§2.1)

3.2 Fabrication of the composites

A method for processing the composites was developed. It allowed the preparation of samples in which the length of the fibers ranged from a few micrometers up to a few millimeters. This method may also be used for composites with any other kind of particles. The method consists in freezing a mixture of chopped carbon fibers and polymer dissolved in a solvent. The solid solvent is then sublimated and the remaining porous material hot-pressed. Here again, the pressing step gave rise to the same strong orientation of the fibers as in the felts. A complete description of the method is given elsewhere (5).

4. RESULTS

4.1 Out-of-plane thermal conductivity

Out-of-plane thermal conductivity measurements performed on the composites and on the felts are reported on in figure 3 and table 1. The values given for the felts have been corrected to account for the contribution of the VespelTM container.

Furthermore, linear regressions were computed and yielded the relations (1) and (2).

$$0.0003 + 0.01377 \text{ Vf}[\%] = K_{\text{out-of-plane}} \quad (1) \quad \text{for the felt}$$

$$0.2020 + 0.01390 \text{ Vf}[\%] = K_{\text{out-of-plane}} \quad (2) \quad \text{for the composite}$$

4.2. In-plane thermal conductivity

In-plane thermal conductivity measurements performed on the composites and on the felts are reported on in figure 4. Here again, linear regressions were computed and yielded the relations (3) and (4).

$$-0.16354 + 0.0869 \text{ Vf}[\%] = K_{\text{in-plane}} \quad (3) \quad \text{for the felt}$$

$$-0.09208 + 0.4771 \text{ Vf}[\%] = K_{\text{in-plane}} \quad (4) \quad \text{for the composite}$$

Figure 3 : Out-of-plane thermal conductivity of the felts and composites.

Figure 4 : In-plane thermal conductivity of the felts and composites

5. DISCUSSION

First, it is worth noting that the thermal conductivity of the felt is much smaller than the maximum thermal conductivity that could have been expected from the product of that of the fiber thermal conductivity and the fiber volume fraction. Furthermore, in both felts and composites, the thermal conductivity is strongly dependent on the fiber orientation with respect to the direction of measurement.

Finally, in-plane thermal conductivities comparable to that of stainless steel ($\pm 10 \text{ W.m}^{-1}\text{.K}^{-1}$) are attained in the composite.

Let us suppose that the arrays of fibers are the same with and without polymer. Furthermore, if we consider the polymer and the arrays of fibers as two possible paths in parallel for the heat flowing through the sample, we can subtract the thermal conductivity of the polymer from that of the composite (equations 5 and 6 hereunder). Then, comparison between this result and the thermal conductivity of the felt should yield information on the role of polymer.

However, since fiber concentrations are not the same in the felts and in the composites, we decided to use the fiber concentrations from the samples of felts as a basis for the comparison. Then, the equations from linear regressions were used to compute the corresponding thermal conductivities of the different series of samples.

Thus, equation 5 and 6 are :

$$\text{Computed thermal conductivity from equation (2)} - (1-V_f) \times 0.20 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Computed thermal conductivity from equation (4)} - (1-V_f) \times 0.20 \quad (6)$$

Felts : Fiber volume fraction [%]	Felts : Measured K [W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹]	Felts : Computed K from equation (1) [W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹]	Composites : Computed K from equation (2) [W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹]	Hypothetical Felts Computed K from equation (5) [W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹]
3.4	0.030	0.047	0.250	0.050
4.7	0.061	0.065	0.267	0.074
5.6	0.098	0.077	0.280	0.095
6.5	0.100	0.090	0.292	0.101
6.7	0.103	0.092	0.295	0.107
7.6	0.119	0.105	0.308	0.121
8.25	0.080	0.114	0.317	0.128

Table 1 : results of out-of-plane thermal conductivity measurements and computed out-of-plane thermal conductivities of composites.

Comparison of the last and the second column in table 1 shows very little difference between the computed K of the felts from equation (5) and the measured K of felts.

On the other hand, the same calculations on the in-plane thermal conductivity measurements clearly highlight a huge difference. These results are reported on in table 2.

Felts : Fiber volume fraction [%]	Felts : Measured K [W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹]	Felts : Computed K from equation (3) [W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹]	Composites : Computed K from equation (4) [W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹]	Hypothetical Felts Computed K from equation (6) [W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹]
5.2	0.38	0.288	2.4	2.4
11.3	0.52	0.818	5.3	5.1
12.0	1.00	0.879	5.6	5.4
16.0	1.21	1.227	7.5	7.6
16.7	1.39	1.288	7.9	7.7

Table 2 : results of in-plane thermal conductivity measurements and computed in-plane thermal conductivities of composites.

We believe that we observe here a combination of the effects of orientation of the fibers with respect to the heat flux direction and of the polymer between the fibers which helps the heat transfer from one fiber to another. Indeed, it is suggested that the thin coat of polymer surrounding a fair contact between the fibers can effectively enhance the thermal conductance of that contact and hence the thermal conductivity of the composite. However, when the fiber axis is roughly perpendicular to the heat flux direction, the heat can not benefit from the elongated shape of the fibers since it only "sees" the diameter of the fiber instead of the length.

6. CONCLUSION

We have realised a series of chopped pitch-based carbon fibers felts and polycarbonate / pitch-based carbon fiber composites in which the arrays of fibers were about the same. Thermal conductivity measurements were then performed in two perpendicular directions and clearly demonstrated the strong effect of the fiber orientation on the thermal conductivity in both felts and composites.

Furthermore, from the in-plane measurements, we suggested that the polymer surrounding a fair contact between the fibers can effectively enhance the thermal conductance of that contact and hence the thermal conductivity of the composite. In the out-of-plane measurements, this effect was much less pronounced because of the fiber orientation with respect to the measurement direction.

Finally, we showed that in-plane thermal conductivities comparable to that of stainless steel can readily be attained in the composites.

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